

Studies in Quinones. Part VI. Fission of Aromatic Ethers by Sodium Metaperiodate

(Late) D. S. Deorha, V. K. Mahesh*, and (Miss) Sneh Prabha Sareen

The study of the reaction of a few aromatic ethers with sodium metaperiodate has lent support to the assignment of methoxyl group at position 4', i.e. in *para* position to the ether linkage in ring B of nidulin, a metabolite of *Aspergillus nidulans*.

Literature reveals that the degradation of depsidones or their derivative with various reagents yields products from which compounds representing their ring A could be easily obtained, but those representing their ring B are difficult to be isolated. Dean *et al.*¹, however, have recently found in sodium metaperiodate a reagent suitable for the scission of methyl *o*-methylnidulinate (II), a derivative of a depsidone 'nidulin' (I), the reaction furnishing methyl everninate representing its ring A and a chlorohydroxyquinone representing its ring B. Dean *et al.*², established the orientation of groups in ring A of nidulin, but they assigned the four groups (chlorine, methoxyl, methyl, and 1'-methylpropenyl) in its ring B tentatively as in (III) by analogy with known depsidones. The two alkyl groups have recently been shown³ in *para* position to each other, though a definitive evidence for the orientation of methoxyl and chlorine groups is still lacking. On these considerations the chlorohydroxyquinone has been assigned^{1,3} structure (IV) tentatively.

*Present address: Dept. of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 4829.

2. *Ibid.*, 1964, 1432.

3. Deorha and Sareen, unpublished; Bycroft *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 5148.

It is likely that during the reaction of the ester (II) with sodium metaperiodate, the hydroxyl group in position 2' and ether linkage in position 1' are oxidised to furnish 1,2-benzoquinone (V) which can yield the *p*-quinone (IV) only if the methoxyl is at position 4' due to obvious reasons. The alternative structure with methoxyl at 5' is less likely as a compound with a hydroxyl at position 2' and a methoxyl at 5', being more easily oxidisable, would have provided a phenoxyquinone (VI) rather than a hydroxyquinone (IV).

This view now receives support from our studies on the reaction of sodium metaperiodate with phenols (VII: R=Me)⁴ and (VII: R=Ph)⁶ providing 2-hydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone⁷ and with compounds (VIII: R=Me)⁵ and (VIII: R=Ph)⁶, furnishing 2-methoxy⁸- and 2-phenoxy-1,4-benzoquinone¹⁰, respectively, with naphthols (IX)⁴ and (X)⁶, yielding 2-hydroxy-9^a and 2-methoxy-1,4-naphthaquinones^{9b}, respectively.

4. Ungnade and Hein, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1949, 14, 911.
5. Ballo, *Gazzetta*, 1949, 79, 925.
6. Deorha and Sareen, unpublished work.
7. Conant and Fieser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1865.
8. Kahrmann and Hoehn, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1925, 8, 221.
9. (a) Fieser, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3163; (b) Bell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 619.
10. Ungnade and Zilah, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1950, 15, 1106.

The reaction has also been extended to the derivative (XI) of unsubstituted depsidone (XII) to ascertain the general applicability of the reagent in the degradation of depsidones. As expected, salicylic acid and 1,2-benzoquinone (in minute amounts due to its sensitivity to water) have been isolated from the reaction mixture; 2,3,4,5-tetrachloro- and -tetrabromoguaicols have been found to yield 2,3,4,5-tetrachloro- and -tetrabromo-1,2-benzoquinones¹¹ on reaction with the reagent. Owing to mild nature of the reagent and the clean products obtained in the reaction, sodium metaperiodate appears to be the first known reagent, suitable for the scission of depsidones, to furnish products representing both its ring A and ring B. A detailed study of the behaviour of the reagent with some simple depsidones, which we have synthesised, is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lactone of 2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxydiphenyl Ether.—A mixture of salol (2.0 g.), manganese dioxide (8.0 g.), and dry chloroform (50 ml) was refluxed for 42 hr. and then filtered. The residue was washed with hot chloroform. The removal of chloroform from the solution left a residue which was chromatographed over alumina from benzene to afford the first few fractions containing the lactone. This was crystallised from light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) in colorless crystals (40 mg.), m.p. 65° (lit.¹², m.p. 62.5°). $\nu_{\max}$ 1740 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 73.43; H, 3.65. Calc. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$: C, 73.58; H, 3.80%).

2-Methoxycarbonyl-2'-hydroxydiphenyl Ether.—The lactone (0.23 g.) in a solution of sodium methoxide (obtained from 0.12 g. Na in 20 ml of methanol) was heated to boiling for 2 hr. The solution was evaporated. On crystallisation from aqueous methanol, the ester was obtained in prisms (0.20 g.), m.p. 99°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3570 cm^{-1} (OH) and 1736 cm^{-1} (ester). (Found: C, 68.69; H, 4.83. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4$: C, 68.84; H, 4.95%).

2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxydiphenyl Ether.—A mixture of the lactone (0.1 g.), 2*N*-NaOH solution (aq., 10 ml), and dioxane (10 ml) was heated on a boiling water bath till a drop of the solution no longer formed a precipitate on dilution with water. After addition of water (50 ml) the resulting acid was precipitated with 2*N*- H_2SO_4 and purified from a mixture of benzene-petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) (1:1) forming plates (0.05 g.), m.p. 126°. (Found: C, 67.73; H, 4.21. Calc. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$: C, 67.82, H, 3.7%).

Reactions of Sodium Metaperiodate

(i). *With 2,5-Dimethoxyphenol.*—To a solution of 3,6-dimethoxyphenol (2.0 g.) in acetic acid (100 ml) was added sodium metaperiodate (4.0 g.) in acetic acid (60%, 50ml). After keeping the mixture in dark for 24 hr., it was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water till the aqueous phase did not effervesce with aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate and then extracted with aqueous sodium carbonate until the extracts were no longer coloured.

11. Jackson and MacLaurin, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1907, 37, 11.

12. Jackson and Flint, *Ibid.*, 1908, 38, 60.

13. Noyes and Weldon, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 401.

The combined coloured extracts were acidified with 2*N*-HCl and extracted with ether. Evaporation of the dried extract left a gum which on slow crystallisation from petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) afforded 2-hydroxy-1, 4-benzoquinone (1.20 g.), m.p. 130-40°.

Reductive acetylation of the hydroxyquinone furnished 1,2,4-triacetoxybenzene; m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, 97°.

(ii). *With 5-Methoxy-2-phenoxyphenol*.—Under the conditions described above, the reaction with the title phenol furnished 2-hydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone, m.p. 130-40°, characterised by the triacetyl derivative; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above, 97°.

(iii). *With 2-Hydroxy-1,4-dimethoxynaphthalene*.—Following the procedure described above, the naphthol furnished 2-hydroxy-1, 4-naphthaquinone; m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample^{9a}, 192°.

(iv). *With 2,4-Dimethoxyphenol*.—2, 4-Dimethoxyphenol (2.0 g.) was allowed to react with sodium metaperiodate according to the method under (i). After diluting the reactants with water, the mixture was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was washed with water and then with sodium bicarbonate solution. On removing ether from the dried ether extract, the residue was crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) to furnish 2-methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone (1.25 g.); m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample⁹, 145°.

(v). *With 4-Methoxy-2phenoxyphenol*.—Following the procedure under (iv), the reaction with this phenol yielded 2-phenoxy-1, 4-benzoquinone; m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample⁹, 71°.

(vi). *With 1-Hydroxy-2,4-dimethoxynaphthalene*.—Under the conditions described under (iv), the oxidation of this naphthol with sodium metaperiodate provided 2-methoxy-1,4-naphthaquinone; m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample^{9b}, 184°.

(vii). *With 2-Carboxy-2'-hydroxydiphenyl Ether*.—A solution of 2-carboxy-2'-hydroxydiphenyl ether (1.0 g.) in acetic acid (60 ml) was mixed with a solution of sodium metaperiodate (1.0 g.) in acetic acid (60%, 120 ml); the mixture was allowed to react for 1 hr. at 10° and then diluted with water (500 ml) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed several times with water till the aqueous phase was devoid of acidic reaction and then with aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate. The alkaline extracts on being acidified with HCl deposited a white crystalline solid which was crystallised from hot water to provide salicylic acid (0.5 g.); m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, 155°.

The ether solution was washed with water and dried. Removal of the solvent afforded a red solid which was crystallised from benzene to provide 1,2-benzoquinone in poor yields (10 mg.), decomposing on heating at 60-70°.

The quinone reacted with *o*-phenylenediamine to afford phenazine; m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, 171°.

(viii). *With 2,3,4,5-Tetrachloro- and -tetrabromo-guaiacols*.—According to the procedure under (iv), 2, 3, 4, 5-tetrachloro- and -tetrabromo-1,2-benzoquinones were obtained from the respective phenol, melting at 133° and 151°, respectively.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
VIGNAN BHAWAN,
UNIVERSITY OF RAJASTHAN,
JAIPUR

AND
SCHOOL OF CHEMISTRY,
MEERUT COLLEGE,
MEERUT.

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